

Chemical Investigation of the Stem-bark of *Jatropha Gossypifolia* Linn.

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Jatropha gossypifolia Linn. (Family: Euphorbiaceae), originally a native of Brazil¹, is a shrub naturalised in Bengal². Villalba³ examined the bark of the plant and reported the isolation of an alkaloid, jatrophine ($C_{14}H_{20}O_6N$), and an 'isophytosterol' ($C_{27}H_{45}OH$), m.p. 124°, $[\alpha]_D -40^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$).

In this investigation the present workers failed to isolate the above 'isophytosterol', but instead isolated from the neutral fraction of the benzene extract of the stem-bark, β -sitosterol, characterised as its acetate.

Isolation of Neutral Fraction.—Dried and powdered bark of *Jatropha gossypifolia* Linn. (800 g.) was extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet apparatus for 6 hr. The dark green residue was taken up in ether, successively washed with cold 10% aq. NaOH solution and water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to furnish the partially crystalline neutral fraction (5 g.).

β -Sitosterol.—The above neutral fraction (5 g.) was chromatographed over a column of activated alumina (150 g.). On elution with a mixture of benzene and ether (2:3), a greyish yellow crystalline fraction (1.14 g.) was obtained. It was rechromatographed over activated alumina (70 g.). Elution with a mixture of benzene and ether (2:3) furnished a white crystalline solid (0.57 g.) which on several crystallisations from methanol furnished a pure sample of β -sitosterol, m.p. 136-37°, $[\alpha]_D -37^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$) (lit.⁴ m.p. 140°, $[\alpha]_D -36^\circ$).

β -Sitosterol Acetate.—The above β -sitosterol (0.57 g.) was acetylated with acetic anhydride (2 ml) and pyridine (2 ml) in the usual manner. The acetate on crystallisation from acetone furnished β -sitosterol acetate (0.12 g.), m.p. 128°, $[\alpha]_D -38^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol acetate. (Found: C, 81.21; H, 11.32. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%).

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